

INFLUENCE OF ANISOTROPY OF PYROLYTIC CARBON ON EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES OF CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Effective elastic properties of carbon/carbon composites fabricated by chemical vapor infiltration are predicted taking into account the cylindrical orthotropy of pyrolytic carbon layers. Microscopic observations are used to characterize microstructure of the composite. The effects of anisotropy on the overall material response are discussed.

Keywords: carbon/carbon composites, micromechanics, anisotropy, effective properties.

INTRODUCTION

This paper deals with the micromechanical modeling of carbon/carbon composites (C/C) fabricated by chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) of carbon fiber pre-form. The technology of CVI involves synthesis of pyrolytic carbon (PyroC) particles from hydrocarbon gas and their deposition on carbon fibers. The process results in formation of a porous pyrolytic carbon matrix filling space between the fibers. This matrix is organized in the cylindrically orthotropic layers concentrically located around fibers as shown in Fig. 1a. These layers correspond to different degrees of preferred orientation (or texture) of basal planes in PyroC that can be characterized by the degree of optical anisotropy in polarized light microscopy, see [1] and references therein. The number of layers, their width, order and structure are strongly influenced by the parameters of infiltration, such as temperature, pressure, residence time, *etc.*

Figure 1. Example of a fiber surrounded by several layers of PyroC having different levels of texture: from micrograph to model. Based on data from [1].

Previous efforts to predict the effective elastic properties of C/C composites mostly assumed the equivalent isotropic behavior of PyroC [2]. This assumption is useful in the evaluation of contribution of porosity and morphology of the reinforcement to the overall response of the material. However, to analyze the influence of fabrication parameters and to understand local stress concentrations in the composite, the anisotropy and inhomogeneity of the matrix material can not be neglected.

Our approach to predicting the effective elastic properties of C/C composite is based on the solution of the elasticity problem for one fiber surrounded by a number of layers of differently textured cylindrically-orthotropic PyroC, see Fig. 1. By considering mechanical response of this object to several basic load cases (axial tension, transverse hydrostatic tension, axial shear and transverse shear), all components of the overall material stiffness tensor for this cylindrical inclusion can be determined. This result can be used in combination with one of the well developed micromechanical models, either composite cylinder assemblage by Hashin and Rosen [3, 4] or generalized self-consistent scheme by Christensen and Lo [5], to predict the overall composite properties.

General solution of the basic problems is chosen in the form proposed by Hashin [4]. The integration constants in the general solution are determined to satisfy the external boundary conditions and the continuity of displacements and tractions at the interfaces between layers. Such an approach provides not only the overall mechanical properties of the composite, but also the distribution of strains and stresses around fibers for basic loading cases. This information offers a valuable insight on the influence of the PyroC coating microstructure on stress concentrations and possible modes of failure in C/C composite.

In this paper, we demonstrate our approach by considering the axisymmetric problem for a multilayered cylinder subjected to the in-plane transverse hydrostatic loading (tension or compression) and the prescribed axial elongation. We produce explicit analytical formulae for displacements and stresses in all layers. The solution of the elasticity problem is used to determine the effective longitudinal Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and transverse (normal to fiber) bulk modulus of the overall composite material.

ELASTIC FIELDS IN MULTILAYERED COMPOSITE CYLINDER

We consider a material system consisting of a cylindrically-orthotropic or transversely isotropic cylinder of radius R_1 surrounded by $(n-1)$ concentric layers ($R_{k-1} \leq r \leq R_k$, $k = 2, \dots, n$) where r, θ, z are the coordinates in the cylindrical coordinate system as shown in Fig. 2. The layers are assumed to be perfectly bonded, so the displacements and radial components of traction are continuous through the interface between any two adjacent layers. Each k -th layer is cylindrically orthotropic and characterized by stiffnesses $C_{rr}^{(k)}$, $C_{r\theta}^{(k)}$, $C_{rz}^{(k)}$, $C_{\theta\theta}^{(k)}$, $C_{\theta z}^{(k)}$, $C_{zz}^{(k)}$. The height of the cylinder is h ($-h/2 \leq z \leq h/2$). The core cylinder ($r \leq R_1$) is treated as the first layer.

Fig.2. Composite cylinder structure

The cylinder is subjected to the in-plane transverse hydrostatic loading σ_T and the prescribed axial strain ϵ_A . The resulting deformation will be axisymmetric: there will be no angular displacement and the radial displacement will depend upon the radial coordinate only, *i.e.* $u = u(r)$. Equilibrium equation yields the following differential equation for radial displacement $u(r)$:

$$r^2 u'' + r u' - \lambda^2 u + \frac{(C_{rz} - C_{r\theta}) \epsilon_A}{C_{rr}} r = 0, \quad (1)$$

where $\lambda = \sqrt{C_{\theta\theta} / C_{rr}}$ and material constants $C_{rr}, C_{r\theta}, C_{rz}, C_{\theta\theta}$ assume their corresponding values for each layer. The general solution of this ordinary differential equation is given by Hashin [4]:

$$u = A \frac{r^\lambda}{b^{\lambda-1}} + B \frac{b^{\lambda+1}}{r^\lambda} + \beta \epsilon_A r, \quad (2)$$

where $\beta = \frac{C_{rz} - C_{r\theta}}{C_{\theta\theta} - C_{rr}}$ and A and B are the integration constants.

This solution results in the following expressions for normal stress components:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_{rr} &= A(\lambda C_{rr} + C_{r\theta}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\lambda-1} + B(-\lambda C_{rr} + C_{r\theta}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-(\lambda+1)} + [\beta(C_{rr} + C_{r\theta}) + C_{rz}] \varepsilon_A, \\
\sigma_{\theta\theta} &= A(\lambda C_{r\theta} + C_{\theta\theta}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\lambda-1} + B(-\lambda C_{r\theta} + C_{\theta\theta}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-(\lambda+1)} + [\beta(C_{r\theta} + C_{\theta\theta}) + C_{\theta z}] \varepsilon_A, \\
\sigma_{zz} &= A(\lambda C_{rz} + C_{\theta z}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{\lambda-1} + B(-\lambda C_{rz} + C_{\theta z}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{-(\lambda+1)} + [\beta(C_{rz} + C_{\theta z}) + C_{zz}] \varepsilon_A.
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

The integration constants A and B assume different values for each layer: $A_1, B_1, A_2, B_2, \dots, A_n, B_n$. These values can be found from the continuity conditions:

$$\sigma_{rr}^{(k)}(R_k) = \sigma_{rr}^{(k+1)}(R_k), \quad u^{(k)}(R_k) = u^{(k+1)}(R_k). \tag{4}$$

Following the influence matrix approach similar to that used by Hervé and Zaoui [6] for isotropic constituents, we can represent equations (4) in the matrix form:

$$\mathbf{J}_k(R_k) \mathbf{V}_k + \varepsilon_A \mathbf{L}_k = \mathbf{J}_{k+1}(R_k) \mathbf{V}_{k+1} + \varepsilon_A \mathbf{L}_{k+1}, \quad k = 1, \dots, (n-1), \tag{5}$$

where $\mathbf{V}_i = [A_i; B_i]^T$ is the vector of integration constants of an i -th layer ($i = 1, \dots, n$) and vector $\mathbf{L}_i = [\beta_i R_i; \beta_i (C_{rr}^{(i)} + C_{r\theta}^{(i)}) + C_{rz}^{(i)}]^T$ depends on the material properties and external radius of i -th layer. Matrix $\mathbf{J}_i(r)$ is given by:

$$\mathbf{J}_i(r) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{r^{\lambda^{(i)}}}{R_i^{\lambda^{(i)}-1}} & \frac{R_i^{\lambda^{(i)}+1}}{r^{\lambda^{(i)}}} \\ (\lambda^{(i)} C_{rr}^{(i)} + C_{r\theta}^{(i)}) \left(\frac{r}{R_i}\right)^{\lambda^{(i)}-1} & (-\lambda^{(i)} C_{rr}^{(i)} + C_{r\theta}^{(i)}) \left(\frac{r}{R_i}\right)^{-(\lambda^{(i)}+1)} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Representation (5) allows us to construct a recurrent procedure to find all integration constants, and thus obtain the complete displacement and stress fields as given by equations (2) and (3). The procedure is described in the text to follow.

Let us solve matrix equation (5) for the set of integration constants of the $(k+1)$ th layer:

$$\mathbf{V}_{k+1} = \mathbf{N}^{(k+1)} \mathbf{V}_k + \varepsilon_A \mathbf{M}^{(k+1)}, \tag{6}$$

where $\mathbf{N}^{(k+1)} = \mathbf{J}_{k+1}^{-1}(R_k) \cdot \mathbf{J}_k(R_k)$ and $\mathbf{M}^{(k+1)} = \mathbf{J}_{k+1}^{-1}(R_k) [\mathbf{L}_k(R_k) - \mathbf{L}_{k+1}(R_k)]$.

Formula (6) can be utilized to express the integration constants in any $(k+1)$ th layer in terms of integration constants of the 1st layer (inner core cylinder):

$$\mathbf{V}_{k+1} = \mathbf{Q}^{(k+1)} \mathbf{V}_1 + \varepsilon_A \mathbf{P}^{(k+1)}, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{Q}^{(k+1)} = \prod_{j=k+1}^2 \mathbf{N}^{(j)}$, $\mathbf{P}^{(k+1)} = [P_1^{(k+1)} \quad P_2^{(k+1)}]^T$ and the components of $\mathbf{P}^{(k+1)}$ are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P_1^{(k+1)} &= \frac{1}{2\lambda^{(k+1)} C_{rr}^{(k+1)}} \left(\frac{R_{k+1}}{R_k} \right)^{\lambda^{(k+1)}-1} [\beta_k (C_{rr}^{(k)} + C_{r\theta}^{(k)}) + C_{rz}^{(k)} - \beta_{k+1} (C_{rr}^{(k+1)} + C_{r\theta}^{(k+1)}) - C_{rz}^{(k+1)} + \\ &+ (\lambda^{(k+1)} C_{rr}^{(k+1)} - C_{r\theta}^{(k+1)}) (\beta_k - \beta_{k+1})] + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \frac{1}{2\lambda^{(i+1)} C_{rr}^{(i+1)}} \left(\frac{R_{i+1}}{R_i} \right)^{\lambda^{(i+1)}-1} [\beta_i (C_{rr}^{(i)} + C_{r\theta}^{(i)}) + C_{rz}^{(i)} - \\ &- \beta_{i+1} (C_{rr}^{(i+1)} + C_{r\theta}^{(i+1)}) - C_{rz}^{(i+1)} + (\lambda^{(i+1)} C_{rr}^{(i+1)} - C_{r\theta}^{(i+1)}) (\beta_i - \beta_{i+1})] \left(\prod_{j=k+1}^{i+2} \mathbf{N}^{(j)} \right), \\ P_2^{(k+1)} &= -\frac{1}{2\lambda^{(k+1)} C_{rr}^{(k+1)}} \left(\frac{R_k}{R_{k+1}} \right)^{\lambda^{(k+1)}+1} [\beta_k (C_{rr}^{(k)} + C_{r\theta}^{(k)}) + C_{rz}^{(k)} - \beta_{k+1} (C_{rr}^{(k+1)} + C_{r\theta}^{(k+1)}) - C_{rz}^{(k+1)} + \\ &+ (\lambda^{(k+1)} C_{rr}^{(k+1)} + C_{r\theta}^{(k+1)}) (\beta_k - \beta_{k+1})] - \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \frac{1}{2\lambda^{(i+1)} C_{rr}^{(i+1)}} \left(\frac{R_i}{R_{i+1}} \right)^{\lambda^{(i+1)}+1} [\beta_i (C_{rr}^{(i)} + C_{r\theta}^{(i)}) + C_{rz}^{(i)} - \\ &- \beta_{i+1} (C_{rr}^{(i+1)} + C_{r\theta}^{(i+1)}) - C_{rz}^{(i+1)} + (\lambda^{(i+1)} C_{rr}^{(i+1)} + C_{r\theta}^{(i+1)}) (\beta_i - \beta_{i+1})] \left(\prod_{j=k+1}^{i+2} \mathbf{N}^{(j)} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Expanding formula (7) and assigning $B_1 = 0$ for the core cylinder to avoid singularity at the center ($r = 0$), we produce the following representation for the vector of integration constants:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} A_{k+1} \\ B_{k+1} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11}^{(k+1)} & Q_{12}^{(k+1)} \\ Q_{21}^{(k+1)} & Q_{22}^{(k+1)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} A_1 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + \varepsilon_A \begin{Bmatrix} M_1^{(k+1)} \\ M_2^{(k+1)} \end{Bmatrix}.$$

Thus, integration constants of any layer can be expressed in terms of the integration constant A_1 . In particular, for the outer n -th layer:

$$A_n = Q_{11}^{(n)} A_1 + \varepsilon_A P_1^{(n)}, \quad B_n = Q_{21}^{(n)} A_1 + \varepsilon_A P_2^{(n)}.$$

Alternatively, all integration constants can be expressed in terms of A_n . First, we express A_1 as

$$A_1 = \frac{1}{Q_{11}^{(n)}} (A_n - \varepsilon_A P_1^{(n)}).$$

Then, for each i -th layer:

$$\begin{aligned} A_i &= \frac{Q_{11}^{(i)}}{Q_{11}^{(n)}} A_n + \varepsilon_A \left(P_1^{(i)} - \frac{Q_{11}^{(i)}}{Q_{11}^{(n)}} P_1^{(n)} \right), \\ B_i &= \frac{Q_{21}^{(i)}}{Q_{11}^{(n)}} A_n + \varepsilon_A \left(P_2^{(i)} - \frac{Q_{21}^{(i)}}{Q_{11}^{(n)}} P_1^{(n)} \right), \end{aligned} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (8)$$

Using these expressions for the integration constants, displacements and stresses in each layer can be found from formulae (2) and (3) in terms of parameters ε_A and A_n , which are determined from the boundary conditions of the corresponding problem, as shown below.

Longitudinal Deformation of the Cylinder

In the case of longitudinal elongation or contraction of the cylinder ($\varepsilon_z = \varepsilon_A$) with no lateral constraints, the boundary conditions are

$$u_z = \varepsilon_A z, \quad \sigma_{rr}(R_n) = 0. \quad (9)$$

Substituting $r = R_n$ in the expression for the radial component of stress (3), the following equation is obtained:

$$A_n (\lambda^{(n)} C_{rr}^{(n)} + C_{r\theta}^{(n)}) + B_n (-\lambda^{(n)} C_{rr}^{(n)} + C_{r\theta}^{(n)}) + [\beta^{(n)} (C_{rr}^{(n)} + C_{r\theta}^{(n)}) + C_{rz}^{(n)}] \varepsilon_A = 0.$$

This equation contains two integration constants of the n -th layer: A_n and B_n . Expressing B_n in terms of A_n and ε_A by means of the second equation in (8), we derive the expression for the integration constant A_n :

$$A_n = -\frac{\varepsilon_A \left\{ \left(P_2^{(n)} - \frac{Q_{21}^{(n)}}{Q_{11}^{(n)}} P_1^{(n)} \right) \left(-\lambda^{(n)} C_{rr}^{(n)} + C_{r\theta}^{(n)} \right) + \left[\beta^{(n)} \left(C_{rr}^{(n)} + C_{r\theta}^{(n)} \right) + C_{rz}^{(n)} \right] \right\}}{\left(\lambda^{(n)} C_{rr}^{(n)} + C_{r\theta}^{(n)} \right) + \frac{Q_{21}^{(n)}}{Q_{11}^{(n)}} \left(-\lambda^{(n)} C_{rr}^{(n)} + C_{r\theta}^{(n)} \right)}. \quad (10)$$

Transverse hydrostatic loading

For uniform transverse lateral compression or tension of the cylinder, the boundary conditions are

$$u_z(z = \pm h/2) = 0, \quad \sigma_r(R_n) = \sigma_T. \quad (11)$$

The first condition of (11) defines the plane strain mode of deformation so that $\varepsilon_A = 0$. The second condition can be utilized to produce the equation for the integration constants A_n and B_n . Substituting the expanded expression from (11) for $r = R_n$, we obtain:

$$A_n \left(\lambda^{(n)} C_{rr}^{(n)} + C_{r\theta}^{(n)} \right) + B_n \left(-\lambda^{(n)} C_{rr}^{(n)} + C_{r\theta}^{(n)} \right) = \sigma_T.$$

Expressing B_n in terms of A_n using (8), we produce the desired formula for the integration constant A_n :

$$A_n = \frac{\sigma_T}{\left(\lambda^{(n)} C_{rr}^{(n)} + C_{r\theta}^{(n)} \right) + \frac{Q_{21}^{(n)}}{Q_{11}^{(n)}} \left(-\lambda^{(n)} C_{rr}^{(n)} + C_{r\theta}^{(n)} \right)}. \quad (12)$$

CHARACTERIZATION OF MICROSTRUCTURE

When observed by polarized light microscopy at the micrometer scale, the pyrolytic carbon matrix around fibers appears in the form of cylindrical layers with different widths and optical anisotropy. An increased optical anisotropy correlates with an increased degree of preferred orientation (texture) of basal planes in pyrolytic carbon. Depending on the optical anisotropy, the following classes of texture can be distinguished: isotropic, low, medium and high textured [7]. The texture can be characterized on the sub-micron length scale by selected area electron diffraction (SAED) in a transmission electron microscope by measuring orientation angles (OAs) [8]. OA ranges $1.4 \leq OA \leq \pi$, $0.88 \leq OA \leq 1.4$ and $OA \leq 0.88$ correspond to low, medium and high textured carbon, respectively.

Let us consider C/C specimen manufactured at the University of Karlsruhe by chemical vapor infiltration of carbon fiber felts at methane pressure of 5 kPa (see Reznik *et al.* [8], where this particular composite is designated as Mat_A). To obtain OA as function of the distance to fiber surface, the SAED investigations were performed with the selected area aperture allowing the analysis of a specimen area of about 550 nm in diameter, see Fig. 1b.

The measured values of OA were utilized to determine the anisotropic mechanical properties of the matrix material around fiber. Based on the value of OA, the sets of the elastic moduli were calculated by applying the analytical modeling procedure developed in [9]. The basic idea of this procedure is to represent the material at the nanolevel as a system of coherent domains of carbon basal planes. The orientation of these domains is described by the experimentally observed OA value which corresponds to the width at half maximum of the orientation on the distribution curve. The mechanical properties of the domains are assumed to be those of highly ordered pyrolytic graphite (Viering *et al.* [10]). The overall properties of differently textured pyrolytic carbon are obtained by applying the homogenization procedure for aggregates of domains. A more detailed presentation of this procedure can be found in Piat *et al.* [9]. The resulting distribution of the layers having different (orthotropic) material properties is shown in Fig.1c, and their stiffness components in GPa are provided in Table 1 ([11]). The properties of the T300 carbon fiber are taken from [12].

Table 1. Mechanical properties of constituents in C/C composite.

Layer	R_{i+1}	C_{rr}	$C_{\theta\theta}$	C_{zz}	C_{rt}	C_{tz}	C_{zr}
Fiber	5	15.361	224.987	224.987	9.756	63.082	9.756
2	5.8	25.166	37.189	37.189	22.362	19.004	22.362
3	9.8	23.863	38.496	38.496	22.272	18.466	22.272
4	10.8	24.953	37.300	37.300	22.332	18.911	22.332
5	11.18	24.189	38.096	38.096	22.309	18.609	22.309

MICROMECHANICAL MODELING OF C/C COMPOSITES

The effective properties of a bundle of unidirectional CVI-densified carbon fibers can be determined if the solution of the elasticity problem for multilayered cylinder is known. These properties can then be used as a basic building block in micromechanical modeling of C/C composites having various properties and fiber orientation patterns.

To obtain the effective properties of the unidirectional infiltrated carbon fibers, we use the composite cylinder assemblage model introduced by Hashin and Rosen [3, 4]. The effective moduli are determined by assigning certain choices of homogeneous boundary conditions in displacements (or tractions). If these conditions result in a state of stress with homogeneous tractions (or displacements) on the corresponding boundaries, the

effective moduli are given by the relations between the volume average strains and stresses.

The axisymmetric analysis procedure presented in the ‘‘Elastic Fields’’ section enables us to determine three material parameters of the equivalent transversely isotropic material: longitudinal Young’s modulus and Poisson’s ratio and transverse bulk modulus. Relating average stresses and strains in a composite cylinder subjected to boundary conditions (9) provides values for axial parameters:

$$E_L = \frac{\langle \sigma_{zz} \rangle}{\varepsilon_A}, \quad \nu_L = -\frac{u(R_n)}{\varepsilon_A R_n}, \quad (13)$$

where $\langle \sigma_{zz} \rangle$ is the axial stress averaged over the cylinder cross section.

Transverse bulk modulus K_T is found using boundary conditions (11):

$$K_T = \frac{\sigma_T R_n}{2u(R_n)}. \quad (14)$$

Let us evaluate how anisotropy of PyroC layers influences predictions for these material parameters. We consider the carbon fiber/PyroC matrix system described in the previous section. Substituting values from the Table 1 into (13) we obtain that $E_L = 59.525 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_L = 0.3792$. If the PyroC is assumed to be isotropic, the equivalent Young’s modulus and Poisson’s ratio of the matrix material can then be found from the rule of mixture as $E_m = 23.404 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_m = 0.409$. These values result in the prediction for the transverse bulk modulus $K_T = 54.368 \text{ GPa}$. However, explicit calculation using equation (13) that takes into account anisotropic properties of PyroC layers produces noticeably lower estimate of the transverse bulk modulus, namely, $K_T = 27.196 \text{ GPa}$. Thus, neglecting the orthotropic layered nature of PyroC in C/C composites may cause significant overestimates (up to several times, as in this example) of the effective transverse material moduli in the infiltrated carbon bundles.

CONCLUSIONS

A closed-form analytical solution of the axisymmetric elasticity problem for fibers surrounded by multiple cylindrically orthotropic layers was proposed. This solution was utilized to predict the effective elastic properties of unidirectional bundles of carbon fibers surrounded by PyroC matrix of varying texture. It was shown that neglecting the anisotropic nature of PyroC material may result in significant inaccuracies in predicted values of certain material parameters.

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